

Original Article

Workplace Incivility and its Effect on Faculty Commitment: A Comparative Study Across Universities

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Abstract

This study aimed to explore and compare the levels of workplace incivility and organizational commitment among faculty members working in public and private universities at the higher education level. The increasing concern over disrespectful and uncivil behavior in academic institutions has created challenges for faculty well-being and professional engagement. Faculty commitment is essential for institutional success, and workplace incivility may undermine that commitment. Quantitative research methods were used in this study. Design to examine the relationship between workplace incivility and the commitment level of faculty members working at higher education institutions. The population of the study included faculty members from public and private universities level. The analysis of data of the quantitative about a comparative study of workplace incivility and commitment level among faculty. The summary of the study including process, the methodology it also includes the analysis of the relationship of workplace incivility among faculty members of university. The purpose of the research is to examine the consequences of the finding, draw conclusion, and provide useful recommendation about the workplace incivility and commitment level among faculty. The organizational commitment of faculty is adversely affected by experiences of incivility, which may impact teaching quality, research productivity, and institutional loyalty. Faculty in private universities, where incivility is comparatively lower, appear to have stronger emotional and professional ties to their institutions. Creating a respectful, supportive, and inclusive work environment is essential for strengthening faculty commitment and performance.

Keywords: Comparative, Study, Workplace, Incivility, Commitment, Faculty, Universities,

Introduction

In recent years, workplace behavior and organizational culture have gained significant attention in higher education institutions due to their direct impact on employee well-being, job satisfaction, and institutional performance. Among the various challenges faced by academic faculty, workplace incivility has emerged as a subtle yet damaging phenomenon. Workplace incivility refers, such as disrespect, discourtesy, exclusion, and belittlement, which violates norms of mutual respect in the workplace. Although these behaviors may seem minor in isolation, their cumulative effect can lead to a toxic environment, psychological distress, and reduced professional productivity.

Incivility and Commitment

Numerous studies have shown that female faculty members often encounter more frequent and severe forms of incivility compared to their male colleagues (Cortina et al., 2001; Settles et al., 2012). This can manifest as being overlooked in meetings, interrupted during discussions, or not receiving proper recognition for their contributions. In the Pakistani context, gender-based bias and patriarchal workplace culture may amplify these issues. For example, (Ahmed & Sajid, 2020) found that female faculty members in public sector universities often reported

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microaggressions, lack of career support and exclusion from decision-making processes factors that affect their affective and normative commitment.

Workplace Incivility & Commitment Level Among Faculty

Unfortunately, a lot of stakeholders faculty, students, and administrative staff do not realise how their destructive actions affect other people. Furthermore, they lack the necessary equipment to manage and/or deal with these kinds of difficult situations. While earlier studies in this field have primarily examined student-initiated classroom incivility, the current study concentrated on the detrimental consequences that incivility can have, even when the targets and instigators are members of the teaching faculty. As a result, incivility in higher education is a significant issue that requires attention.

Incivility in the workplace has become a pervasive issue, affecting various industries and professions, including higher education. Incivility is a growing problem that can have serious consequences for individuals, teams, and organizations. Faculty incivility, in particular, has been linked to decreased job satisfaction, reduced productivity, and a negative impact on student learning outcomes. (Pearson & Porath 2019).

Commitment level of faculty refers to the degree to which faculty members engage in sharing their thoughts, opinions, and expertise through various channels, such as: Faculty members provide constructive feedback to students. Faculty members offer insightful comments on colleagues research or teaching Faculty members contribute to departmental or university-wide discuss Faculty members share their expertise and engage in productive dialogue with colleagues. Faculty members provide guidance and feedback to the students. Faculty members participate in online discussions, sharing their knowledge and expertise Faculty members provide thoughtful comments and suggestions. Civility being practiced within vaticus Professional realms reshaping in heightened levels of burnout and withdrawal or MemoverItemios.(Manzoor , 2020)

Workplace incivility has attracted a considerable attention from management Practitioners and scholars in recent years (Huang & Lin, 2019). Another study performed in the UK reported that stress associated with uncivil workplace Behavior generally costs the organizations as much as approximately 1.3 billion of Euros annually (Yeung & Griffin, 2008). In the past few years, managers and researchers raised their concerns Regarding the rising level of workplace incivility and the acute devastation it causes to the societal fabric Of organizations (Porath & Pearson, 2013). All Troublesome acts falling in the category of Incivility must be addressed before these behaviors turn into Aggression and endanger the healthy academic work environment (Clark and Springer 2010)

Workplace Incivility in Organizations

To establish more humanistic workplaces, incivility that is, rude conduct, disrespect for superiors, and a lack of regard for coworkers needs to be dissected and explained. The internal mechanisms of the members of an organisation have the power to tear or invert the fabric of social order. Critical thinking and introspection can yield insights that lead to more effective organisations and change processes rather than viewing these differing viewpoints as noise and deviation.(Powell & Rerup, 2017).

A comparative study of workplace Incivility and commitment level among faculty in higher education can reveal valuable insights into how negative behaviors influence dedication to their institutions. Workplace incivility among faculty, such as dismissive behavior, undermining colleagues, or exclusion from decision-making, can erode trust and create a toxic work environment. This environment, in turn, affects job satisfaction and professional dedication, ultimately impacting the commitment level of faculty members. Reduce productivity and collaborations. Damage relationships and reputations. faculty incivility can have a negative Impact on student learning outcomes, including decreased motivation, decreased engagement, and Decreased academic achievement.(Rowland & Srisukho 2009)

- ✓ **Commitment Level:** The commitment level among faculty can be described through three dimensions:
- ✓ **Affective Commitment** (emotional attachment to the institution),
- ✓ **Continuance Commitment** (perceived costs of leaving the institution),
- ✓ **Normative Commitment** (feeling of obligation to remain).

Studies often find a correlation between incivility and reduced commitment, particularly affecting affective and normative commitment. For instance, if faculty members frequently face rude or dismissive behaviors, their sense of belonging and loyalty weakens. Conversely, environments that foster mutual respect and recognition strengthen faculty commitment, encouraging collaborative engagement and long-term retention. A university department

where junior faculty members are regularly interrupted or excluded from meetings might see these individuals become less committed, only fulfilling their basic duties without showing initiative. Techniques and different Strategies to enhance commitment level include creating an inclusive culture, recognizing the achievements, and providing opportunities for growth and development. “incivility in nursing education is a serious Concern that can have significant consequences for students, faculty, and patients.”(Luparell 2017),

Review of the Related Literature

Workplace Incivility refers to low-intensity, deviant behavior in the workplace that violates norms of respect but whose intent to harm is ambiguous or unclear. These behaviors are often subtle, indirect, and not openly hostile, making them difficult to address formally. “Workplace incivility is is low-level deviant behaviour that violates workplace rules for mutual respect and has unclear intent to hurt the target. Pearson and Andersson (1999).It has been frequently observed that workplace rudeness has a negative correlation with organisational commitment (Reio&Trudel, 2013; Zahoor et al., 2022). Affective commitment (emotional connection), normative commitment (feeling compelled to stay), and continuation commitment (perceived cost of leaving) are all components of organisational commitment (Benbow et al., 2024).Research shows that being treated rudely by coworkers or superiors reduces an employee's sense of loyalty to the company (Mahmood et al., 2023; Guo et al., 2020).For example, a study conducted on female employees in public universities found that rudeness from coworkers and supervisors considerably lowers organisational commitment (Mahmood et al., 2023). Likewise, studies conducted in the Indian service industry discovered a negative correlation between organisational commitment and workplace rudeness (Hussain et al., 2023). Various other aspects further affect the impact degree of rudeness. Take for example, the link between workplace rudeness and organisational outcomes could be mediated by Psychological capital (PsyCap) which consists of resilience, optimism, hope, and self-efficacy (Zahoor et al., 2022).

Factors Mediating and Moderating the Relationship Between Incivility and Commitment

The bond that exists between organisational commitment and workplace rudeness is impacted by so many mediating and moderating dynamics. Incivility at the workplace (WINC) and Organizational Identification (OID) can be mediated by Affective Organizational Commitment (AC) and Perceived Insider Status (PIS) as well (Ismail & Ali, 2016). Specifically, affective commitment and perceived insider status aid as mediators in the way workplace incivility affects organizational identification (Ismail & Ali, 2016) (Tran, 2025).

Also, mediation by work engagement and job fatigue, as noted in Vietnamese business school libraries, goes to show the gap between workplace rudeness and organizational commitment (Chris et al., 2022). As per Chris et al. (2022), rudeness at the workplace can lead to increased burnout and decline in engagement which leads to reduced organizational commitment. Incivility along with other dimensions like job satisfaction and even affective commitment is mediated by perceived organizational support (POS) (Changguo&Jianmin, 2013). In Changguo and Jianmin (2013), employees showcased that lack of support because of rudeness leads to declining commitment and job satisfaction.

Relationship Between Incivility & Commitment

Many studies have shown that workplace incivility has a negative link with organizational commitment. (Lim & Teo,2009)Employees with higher levels of incivility tended to report greater emotional disconnection as well as higher intent to leave the organization (Samier,2016).

In Pakistani universities, studies have shown a rise in faculty stress and discontent due to lack of respect, favoritism, and poor communication, all indicators of workplace incivility (Khan et al., 2020). However, limited research has explored how this incivility impacts commitment levels, highlighting a key gap addressed by the present study. The Relationship Between Workplace Incivility and Faculty has become a pervasive in academic institutions, affecting faculty members’ productivity, job satisfaction, and Overall well-being. Although international literature has extensively covered the impact of workplace incivility on employee outcomes, there is a scarcity of comparative research in the higher education sector in Pakistan focusing on how incivility influences the organizational commitment of faculty. Furthermore, gender and institutional type (public vs. private) are underexplored as moderating factors.

Research Objectives

- To investigate the nature of workplace incivility among faculty at higher level.
- To compare the commitment level among faculty experiencing at workplace incivility at higher level.

Research Methodology

The study employed a quantitative, comparative research design. This design is suitable for identifying differences in workplace incivility and organizational commitment across different groups (e.g., public vs. private institutions, male. female faculty). The use of standardized instruments and statistical techniques allows for objective comparisons and relationship analysis. The population consisted of faculty members working in public and private universities/colleges at the higher education level in Punjab, Pakistan. This included lecturers, assistant professors, associate professors, and professors from various disciplines. This study focuses on the public and private two sector universities. Where Public University is Women University and private university is virtual university of Pakistan. Simple of this study 20 faculty members in women’s university and Vitural university Multan campus. To carry out this study, simple random sampling techniques were used in order to select the sample from the population. A standardized questionnaire used to measure the academic discrimination experienced by faculty. Data were collected through self-administered questionnaires, either in printed form or via online platforms (e.g., Google Forms), depending on the accessibility of faculty members.Descriptive Statistics (Frequency, Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation, Chi-squre test) to summarize the data.

Data Analysis

Table 1

To Investigate the Nature and Extend of Workplace Incivility among Faculty

Statement	Mean	StdDev
Incivility among faculty effects motivation at work	1.45	.788
Faculty members show a lack of appreciation for each other’s work	1.46	.801
Staff observed favoritism among members	1.66	8.28
There is a lack of collaboration among faculty members	1.85	1.00
Faculty isolated by other faculty members	1.78	.941
Faculty members frequently interrupt each other in meeting	1.60	.955
Staff experienced disrespect from other faculty members	2.15	.940

Figure 1

Bar Chart of Responses about Workplace Incivility among Faculty

The findings in Table 1 reveal a concerning presence of workplace incivility among faculty members, with varying degrees of severity. The lowest mean score ($M = 1.45$) for the statement “Incivility among faculty affects motivation at work” indicates a strong agreement that such behaviors negatively impact professional motivation. Similarly, the perception that “Faculty members show a lack of appreciation for each other’s work” ($M = 1.46$) reinforces the presence of unrecognized contributions, which can lower morale and collegial trust. The issue of favoritism is also evident, though the unusually high standard deviation ($SD = 8.28$) for the statement “Staff observed favoritism among members” suggests highly inconsistent responses, possibly due to varied experiences or misreporting of data. Additionally, a lack of collaboration ($M = 1.85$) and feelings of isolation ($M = 1.78$) point to strained professional relationships and exclusionary practices. Interruptions during meetings ($M = 1.60$) also indicate a lack of professional courtesy and respect during faculty interactions. The highest mean score ($M = 2.15$) corresponds to the statement “Staff experienced disrespect from other faculty members,” suggesting that open acts of disrespect are more frequently experienced and possibly normalized in the workplace environment.

Table 2

To Compare Commitment Level among Faculty Experiencing Workplace Incivility

Statement	Mean	StdDev
Faculty actively participate in meeting	2.14	1.24
Sometime take initiative in contribution to faculty discussion	2.10	1.19
Professional interactions foster inclusivity and support	2.11	.930
Staying with the institution supports personal and professional growth	2.12	.885
Faculty actively participate in Assignment given by Department	1.86	.938
Sometime Faculty member speak against during class	2.18	1.31
Always encourage student to participate in class discussion	1.82	1.23

Figure 2

Bar Chart of Responses about Commitment Level among Faculty

The data presented in Table 2 highlights the overall low level of commitment among faculty members experiencing workplace incivility. The mean scores for all statements range between 1.82 and 2.18, indicating a generally weak sense of involvement and dedication. For instance, the statement “Faculty actively participate in meetings” received a mean score of 2.14, suggesting limited participation in institutional activities. Similarly, the

mean score of 2.10 for “Sometimes take initiative in contribution to faculty discussion” reflects a lack of proactive engagement in academic discussions. The perception that “Professional interactions foster inclusivity and support” also remains low ($M = 2.11$), implying that a lack of supportive workplace relationships may be affecting commitment levels. Furthermore, only a small portion of faculty agree that “Staying with the institution supports personal and professional growth” ($M = 2.12$), which indicates weakened emotional attachment and long-term commitment. Particularly concerning is the low engagement in departmental responsibilities ($M = 1.86$) and low encouragement of student participation in class ($M = 1.82$), both of which signal disengagement from core professional duties. Interestingly, the highest mean (2.18) is observed in the statement “Sometimes faculty members speak against during class,” which may point to rising discontent or resistance.

Table 3*Chi-Square Test Results*

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Person Chi-Square	23.289 ^a	16	.106
Likelihood Ratio	25.899	16	.055
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.634	1	.201
N of Valid Cases	200		

The Pearson Chi-Square test was conducted to examine whether there is a significant association between workplace incivility and faculty commitment levels. The results show a Chi-Square value of 23.289 with 16 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.106. Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 significance level, the result is not statistically significant. This means there is no strong evidence of a meaningful association between workplace incivility and commitment levels in this sample. Similarly, the Likelihood Ratio value of 25.899 with a p-value of 0.055 is slightly closer to significance but still exceeds the 0.05 threshold. This also suggests no statistically significant relationship. The Linear-by-Linear Association value is 1.634 with a p-value of 0.201, indicating no significant linear trend between the variables, which is particularly relevant if the data are ordinal. Workplace incivility is a serious concern in higher education institutions, particularly in public universities. The organizational commitment of faculty is adversely affected by experiences of incivility, which may impact teaching quality, research productivity, and institutional loyalty. Faculty in private universities, where incivility is comparatively lower, appear to have stronger emotional and professional ties to their institutions. Creating a respectful, supportive, and inclusive work environment is essential for strengthening faculty commitment and performance.

Conclusions

Workplace incivility is a serious concern in higher education institutions, particularly in public universities. The organizational commitment of faculty is adversely affected by experiences of incivility, which may impact teaching quality, research productivity, and institutional loyalty. Faculty in private universities, where incivility is comparatively lower, appear to have stronger emotional and professional ties to their institutions. Creating a respectful, supportive, and inclusive work environment is essential for strengthening faculty commitment and performance. Furthermore, the word cloud highlights values like constructive behavior, safety, professionalism, and collaboration, which are vital in reducing workplace incivility and ensuring a healthy work culture. Lesser but relevant terms such as incivility, behavioral concerns, balance & empathy indicate that addressing challenges and fostering emotional intelligence are also critical for long-term sustainability. In summary, the word cloud captures the essence of a supportive and respectful academic environment, built through intentional institutional practices, proactive leadership, and ongoing faculty development. It underscores the need for access, equity, and constructive engagement to enhance both individual and organizational effectiveness.

Discussion

This incivility describes all racism, xenophobia and discrimination in the workplace. Academic incivility negatively affects academics' physical and mental health and performance on their jobs, job satisfaction, personal wellbeing, intentions to quit and professional identity. As private universities increase their global influence, it is essential to understand the intricacies of civility issues inside their academic institutions. (Powell & Rerup, 2017). Data from the interviews were analyzed with given codes, categories, and themes. The findings showed that

academic workplace incivility negatively impacts academics' emotional well-being, job performance, and interpersonal relationships. For the coping strategy, academics often employ several strategies when faced with incivility. These strategies include directly confronting the instigators, actively avoiding them, seeking support from their social networks, and experiencing emotional reactions such as dissatisfaction and frustration. This study focus on the workplace incivility and faculty commitment which explores the link between harmful behaviors and faculty relationship. (Shin & Hur, 2019). Workplace Incivility refers to low-intensity, deviant behavior in the workplace that violates norms of respect but whose intent to harm is ambiguous or unclear. These behaviors are often subtle, indirect, and not openly hostile, making them difficult to address formally. "Workplace incivility is low-intensity deviant behavior with ambiguous intent to harm the target, in violation of workplace norms for mutual respect." (Andersson & Pearson, 2002) Research by Cortina et al. (2001) showed that persistent incivility leads to increased stress, emotional exhaustion, and decreased job satisfaction. In academic institutions, such behavior can arise from competition, hierarchical disparities, and administrative pressures (Keenan & Newton, 2013). Workplace incivility in the staff members has become a more complicated issue in academic institutions, undermining the collaboratively and respectful environment which is more necessary for effective learning process, and service. When faculty members experience incivility, they are likely to feel more disappointed, shameless, unsupported, and marginalized, which results shows to decreased job satisfaction, reduced productivity, and create situation to leave their institution as soon as possible. Decreased job satisfaction: Feeling unhappy, unfulfilled, and disconnected from one's work.

Recommendations of the study

- Future studies can explore the qualitative dimensions of workplace incivility through interviews or focus groups to gain deeper insights.
- A longitudinal study could help observe how incivility and commitment evolve over time.
- Research could also examine the role of organizational culture, leadership style, and emotional intelligence in moderating the effects of workplace incivility.
- Similar studies can be conducted in other provinces or countries to compare institutional climates across regions.
- Encourage mentoring, counseling, and faculty development programs to enhance commitment and well-being.
- Promote a positive organizational culture based on empathy, collaboration, and recognition of faculty contributions.

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